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OPTIMIZING QUEUING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS FOR ENHANCED SERVICE EFFICIENCY IN A GOVERNMENT HEALTH INSURANCE AGENCY

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ABSTRACT

Health insurance agencies play a crucial role in providing universal health coverage to people. Long queues and waiting times make it difficult for services to be efficient and for members to be satisfied. Research findings indicate significant issues with staffing allocation, process repetition, and inefficient break scheduling, contributing to long queues. This study addresses these challenges by employing queuing theory models, simulation software, and process flow chart analysis. An action research approach is utilized, involving stakeholders and employing tools such as time and motion study. Data is gathered through interviews, observations, and secondary sources. Proposed solutions include balanced break schedules, checklist implementation, and separate queuing systems. These strategies are shown to reduce waiting times, cost of waiting time, processing times, and travel distances, and an increase in members served, thereby improving service efficiency. Implementing these solutions can effectively address queuing challenges, leading to improved service delivery and member satisfaction at health insurance agencies. It is crucial to address staffing allocation, process repetition, and break scheduling issues to optimize service efficiency and ensure timely access to essential healthcare services for all stakeholders.

Keywords: *Queuing Theory, Process Flow Chart Analysis, Service Efficiency, Simulation Software*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most unpleasant but inevitable experiences in daily life is waiting for assistance. When we wait in line at banks, fast-food restaurants, hair salons, medical facilities, insurance agencies, or retail establishments, it immediately affects how we perceive the quality of the service (Obermeier et al., 2020). A well-designed queuing system reduces short queue lengths and waiting times, which enhances the service quality and customer satisfaction. There is also an increase in efficiency, leading to higher productivity and better utilization of resources (Amelia et al., 2021).

Customer dissatisfaction with the service has far-reaching consequences, affecting the entire industry. Prolonged wait times or long queue lines not only frustrate potential consumers to leave, but they may damage the company's brand image, encouraging negative opinions among current and future customers. Furthermore, the negative impacts aren't limited to consumers; long lineups may decrease employee morale, resulting in lower work satisfaction and productivity. So, the company needs to fix service problems and reduce wait times to keep customers happy and maintain a good reputation (Burodo et al., 2021).

An analytical method to problem-solving and decision-making that is effective in organizational management is operations research (OR). Mathematical analysis breaks issues down and delivers step-by-step answers. When it comes to decision-making OR is more effective than standard software and data analytics methodologies (Lewis, 2019). Queuing theory, a mathematical framework, serves as a crucial tool for examining varied system types and their performance regarding service quality. From complicated queues inside broad network systems to the investigation of service chains, queuing theory gives insights into system behavior. It permits the examination of numerous parameters such as waiting times, resource use, and system throughput (Jiang et al., 2019).

This study aims to address the issues of extended queue lengths and prolonged waiting times observed during Public Assistance and Complaints Desk (PACD)/screening, membership, and payment section at the government health insurance agency. To propose effective solutions to the problems associated with service planning and scheduling in this industry, data will be gathered utilizing the M/M/s queuing theory model and process flow chart analysis. Data collection occurred over a single day with a nine (9) hour operation. The researcher conducted a comparative analysis to assess the disparities between the current system and the proposed system, with the objective of determining their significance in enhancing efficiency and customer satisfaction levels.

Based on the research of Bahrami et al. (2020), shows that the use of queuing theory models improves the satisfaction of the patients in terms of receiving services in a healthcare facility. Many existing studies show how queuing theory and healthcare management have extensively explored strategies to reduce waiting times and improve efficiency in healthcare settings such as hospitals and clinics; however, there is a lack of studies addressing queue management in health insurance agencies. This study's

significance lies in its potential to enhance service delivery at the case company by reducing waiting times and queue lengths, thereby improving overall customer experience and satisfaction, particularly in healthcare insurance, where timely access to services is crucial. This study also contributes by extending the applicability of existing knowledge and recommendations relevant to this industry.

Research Questions

In the service industry, efficient queuing management systems are essential for ensuring customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. However, inadequate queuing strategies often result in prolonged wait times, dissatisfied customers, and subpar service delivery. Using Fishbone Diagram and 5 Why's Analysis, this research aims to uncover critical insights into the root causes of these issues. By identifying these root causes, the study seeks to develop and implement queuing strategies to reduce waiting time and long queue lengths, ultimately enhancing service efficiency, customer satisfaction, and ensuring timely access to essential healthcare services for all stakeholders. Specifically, this research tried to address subsequent inquiries:

1. What are the main factors contributing to prolonged waiting times and excessive queue lengths at the government health insurance agency?

1.1. How do manpower availability, particularly during breaks and staff allocation, and management practices like break scheduling and frontliner allocation impact queue lengths during operational hours?

1.2. How do process inefficiencies, such as repetition and inadequate transmission of information, prolong transaction times and elongate queues?

2. How can queuing strategies be developed and implemented to reduce waiting time and long queue lengths at the government health insurance agency, thereby enhancing service efficiency and customer satisfaction?

2.1. What strategies can be employed to improve manpower allocation and deployment, as well as optimize methods to streamline processes and reduce transaction times, thereby minimizing queue lengths during operational hours?

2.2. What managerial interventions are necessary to improve break scheduling and staff allocation, leading to more efficient frontline deployment and shorter queues?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at a government health insurance agency, focusing on addressing issues related to extended queue lengths and prolonged waiting times observed during various operational phases, including Public Assistance and Complaints

Desk (PACD)/screening, membership, and payment sections. The sampling method involved purposive selection of participants directly involved in the operations of the government health insurance agency. Data were gathered through a combination of observation and interviews. Direct observation of the process flow from member application to the payment section provided insights into existing challenges. Interviews with personnel addressed issues related to long queues and service time. Various tools and methods were used for data collection. A phone and stopwatch combo recorded customer arrival and service times, offering insights into interaction durations. Additionally, a handheld tally counter tracked member arrivals per minute, systematically measuring entry flow.

The arrival time, service time, and transportation of members lacking qualifications were all determined using Industrial Engineering techniques including time and motion studies. Data analysis was conducted using the Queuing theory model (M/M/S): (FCFS/ ∞/∞) to calculate average arrival and service rates, with the mean statistical tool in Microsoft Excel used to compute necessary values. The analysis process involves comparing the present queuing system with the proposed one to reveal significant differences in waiting time, line length, and distance saved. The suggested queuing model demonstrates decreased waiting time and shorter lineups, highlighting potential advantages for service efficiency. Visual aids such as tables and charts facilitate thorough insights and comprehension. Design planning includes defining objectives, literature study, data assessment, and solution design, aiming to increase service efficiency by addressing waiting time and queue length issues through queuing theory concepts and process improvements. Testing involves comparative analysis, time study, motion analysis, simulation software, and sensitivity analysis to assess system efficiency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Frontliners' Break Scheduling

Table 1.

Current Frontliners' Break Scheduling

PACD/Screening Section						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate	Utilization Factor	%
1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	73	1.2167	0.7522	1.6175	161.75
1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	52	0.8667	0.7522	1.1522	115.22
Membership Section						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate	Utilization Factor	%
2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	33	0.5460	0.2316	1.1788	117.88
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	18	0.3008	0.2316	0.6494	64.94
Payment Section						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate	Utilization Factor	%
1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	10	0.1722	0.2373	0.7258	72.58
1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	8	0.1317	0.2373	0.5552	55.52

The table 1 illustrates that the current scheduling of the frontliners' breaks results in long queues in both batches within the PACD/screening and membership sections, as the utilization factor of the frontliners exceeds 80%. In the payment section, one (1) frontliner is generally sufficient to assist members during those hours. However, since some members have numerous transactions that consume significant time, it is necessary to include two (2) frontliners to lessen the longer waiting time for members in the queue.

Comparative Analysis of Frontliners' Utilization Factor

Table 2.

Hourly Frontliner Utilization Comparison in PACD/Screening

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)	Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
3	8:00 am - 9:00 am	48.01	2	8:00 am - 9:00 am	72.01
3	9:00 am - 10:00 am	40.62	2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	60.93
3	10:00 am - 11:00 am	39.14	2	10:00 am - 11:00 am	58.72
3	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	53.92	2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	80.87
3	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	38.41	2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	57.61
3	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	37.67	2	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	56.50
3	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	45.79	2	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	68.69
3	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	38.41	2	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	57.61
3	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	15.51	2	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	23.26

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
1	8:00 am - 9:00 am	144.02
1	9:00 am - 10:00 am	121.86
1	10:00 am - 11:00 am	117.43
1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	161.75
1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	115.22
1	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	113.00
1	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	137.37
1	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	115.22
1	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	46.53

Interpretation
Underutilized
Balanced
Overutilized
Balanced but causes long queues

Each group of frontliners has a color-coded usage factor, which helps balance their hourly availability. Table 2 shows that three frontliners on the PACD/screening sector is excessive owing to its low utilization factor, resulting in idle frontliners. This section may so have less frontliners. However, allocating just one frontliner exceeds the recommended utilization factor of 80%, resulting in long queues and waiting times for members. This may work in the last hour of the day when consumer arrival is low. Throughout the day, it is advisable to have two (2) counters open to minimize queues and waiting times for members.

Table 3.

Comparison of Utilization Factor of Frontliners/Hour in Membership Section

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)	Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
4	8:00 am - 9:00 am	42.06	3	8:00 am - 9:00 am	56.09
4	9:00 am - 10:00 am	54.74	3	9:00 am - 10:00 am	72.99
4	10:00 am - 11:00 am	66.39	3	10:00 am - 11:00 am	88.53
4	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	58.94	3	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	78.59
4	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	32.47	3	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	43.29
4	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	52.43	3	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	69.91
4	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	56.03	3	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	74.70
4	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	48.83	3	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	65.11
4	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	27.16	3	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	36.21

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)	Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
2	8:00 am - 9:00 am	84.13	1	8:00 am - 9:00 am	168.26
2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	109.49	1	9:00 am - 10:00 am	218.97
2	10:00 am - 11:00 am	132.79	1	10:00 am - 11:00 am	265.58
2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	117.88	1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	235.77
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	64.94	1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	129.88
2	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	104.86	1	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	209.72
2	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	112.06	1	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	224.11
2	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	97.66	1	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	195.33
2	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	54.32	1	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	108.63

Interpretation
Underutilized
Balanced
Overutilized
Balanced but causes long queues

Table 3 illustrates that in the membership section, having four (4) frontliners is acceptable. There are certain hours, such as 10am-11am, where four (4) frontliners are necessary. However, similar to the PACD/screening section, where frontliners may be underutilized, optimization can be achieved by reducing the number of open counters. Operating with only one (1) or two (2) frontliners throughout the day results in a high utilization factor, contributing to longer waiting times and queues. Nevertheless, during off-peak hours like 12pm-1pm and 4pm-5pm, operating with two (2) frontliners is sufficient due to the lower volume of arriving members. To ensure a smooth flow of member assistance throughout the day, maintaining a balanced set of three (3) frontliners available is recommended.

Table 4.
Comparison of Utilization Factor of Frontliners/Hour in Payment Section

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
3	8:00 am - 9:00 am	19.51
3	9:00 am - 10:00 am	24.30
3	10:00 am - 11:00 am	26.20
3	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	24.19
3	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	18.51
3	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	21.40
3	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	23.08
3	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	19.73
3	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	9.70

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
2	8:00 am - 9:00 am	29.26
2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	36.46
2	10:00 am - 11:00 am	39.30
2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	36.29
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	27.76
2	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	32.11
2	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	34.62
2	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	29.60
2	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	14.55

Frontliners	Time	Utilization Factor (%)
1	8:00 am - 9:00 am	58.53
1	9:00 am - 10:00 am	72.91
1	10:00 am - 11:00 am	78.60
1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	72.58
1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	55.52
1	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	64.21
1	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	69.23
1	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	59.20
1	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	29.10

Interpretation	
Underutilized	
Balanced	
Overutilized	
Balanced but causes long queues	

Table 4 shows that for the payment section, operating with three (3) frontliners throughout the day results in a low utilization factor. It is advisable not to add another frontliner unless there is a day with a high volume of arrivals in the future. Operating with only one (1) frontliner achieves a balanced utilization factor; However, some members have multiple transactions, which can lead to longer waiting times and queues for other members in line. Nevertheless, opening one counter during the last hour of the shift is acceptable. Maintaining two (2) frontliners throughout the entire day is the best approach to achieve service efficiency.

Table 5.
Proposed Hourly Staff Allocation

PACD/Screening Section						
Number of Counters Available per hour						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate/min	Utilization Factor	%
2	8:00 am - 9:00 am	65	1.0833	0.7522	0.7201	72.01
2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	55	0.9167	0.7522	0.6093	60.93
2	10:00 am - 11:00 am	53	0.8833	0.7522	0.5872	58.72
2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	73	1.2167	0.7522	0.8087	80.87
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	52	0.8667	0.7522	0.5761	57.61
2	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	51	0.8500	0.7522	0.5650	56.50
2	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	62	1.0333	0.7522	0.6869	68.69
2	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	52	0.8667	0.7522	0.5761	57.61
1	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	21	0.3500	0.7522	0.4653	46.53

Membership Section						
Number of Counters Available per hour						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate/min	Utilization Factor	%
3	8:00 am - 9:00 am	23	0.3897	0.2316	0.5609	56.09
3	9:00 am - 10:00 am	30	0.5071	0.2316	0.7299	72.99
4	10:00 am - 11:00 am	37	0.6151	0.2316	0.6639	66.39
3	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	33	0.5460	0.2316	0.7859	78.59
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	18	0.3008	0.2316	0.6494	64.94
3	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	29	0.4857	0.2316	0.6991	69.91
3	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	31	0.5190	0.2316	0.7470	74.70
3	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	27	0.4524	0.2316	0.6511	65.11
2	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	15	0.2516	0.2316	0.5432	54.32

Payment Section						
Number of Counters Available per hour						
Frontliner	Time	Average Arrival/hour	Mean Arrival Rate/min	Mean Service Rate/min	Utilization Factor	%
2	8:00 am - 9:00 am	8	0.1389	0.2373	0.2926	29.26
2	9:00 am - 10:00 am	10	0.1730	0.2373	0.3646	36.46
2	10:00 am - 11:00 am	11	0.1865	0.2373	0.3930	39.30
2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	10	0.1722	0.2373	0.3629	36.29
2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	8	0.1317	0.2373	0.2776	27.76
2	1:00 pm - 2:00 pm	9	0.1524	0.2373	0.3211	32.11
2	2:00 pm - 3:00 pm	10	0.1643	0.2373	0.3462	34.62
2	3:00 pm - 4:00 pm	8	0.1405	0.2373	0.2960	29.60
1	4:00 pm - 5:00 pm	4	0.0690	0.2373	0.2910	29.10

Based on the comparison of the utilization factor of frontliners per hour in each section, table 5 illustrates the appropriate number of available counters to be opened hourly is determined. Ensuring that the number of available counters remains consistent throughout the day is essential to prevent the accumulation of long queues, particularly as the utilization factor of the frontliners remains below 80% (Rajagopalan, 2016).

Table 6.
Hourly Breaks' Performance Summary in PACD/Screening Section

Performance Rate	11:00 am – 12:00 pm		12:00 pm – 1:00 pm	
	Current	Proposed	Current	Proposed
Frontliner (s)	1	2	1	2
Mean Arrival Rate (λ)	1.2167 member/minute	1.2167 member/minute	0.8667 member/minute	0.8667 member/minute
Mean Service Rate (μ)	0.7522 member/minute	0.7522 member/minute	0.7522 member/minute	0.7522 member/minute
Utilization factor of the entire system (ρ)	161.75%	80.87%	115.22%	57.61%
Probability of zero member in the system (P_0)	-	10.57%	-	26.89%
Average number of members in the queue (L_q)	-	3.0587 members	-	0.5724 members
Average number of members in the system (L_s)	-	4.6762 members	-	1.7246 members

Average waiting time in the queue (W_q)	-	2.5139 minutes	-	0.6604 minutes
Average time a member spends in the system (W_s)	-	3.8433 minutes	-	1.99 minutes

Table 6 explains that for the PACD/screening section, it is essential to have at least two (2) frontliners available. This is because, based on the gathered data, some members take up to seven (7) minutes in asking questions, leading to longer waiting times for members in the queue. The table demonstrates that operating with two (2) frontliners during the first batch enhances the utilization rate from 161.75% to 80.87%, resulting in 3.0587 members in the queue and 4.6762 members in the system. The average waiting time for members in the queue is 2.5139 minutes, while the average time spent by members in the system is 3.8433 minutes. During the second batch, it is crucial to have two (2) counters open, as this improves the utilization rate from 115.22% to 57.61%. As a result, there are 0.5724 members in the queue and 1.7246 members in the system. The average waiting time for members in the queue is 0.6604 minutes, with members spending an average of 1.99 minutes in the system.

Table 7.
Hourly Breaks' Performance Summary in Membership Section

Performance Rate	11:00 am – 12:00 pm		12:00 pm – 1:00 pm	
	Current	Proposed	Current	Proposed
Frontliner (s)	2	3	2	2
Mean Arrival Rate (λ)	0.5460 member/minute	0.5460 member/minute	0.3008 member/minute	0.3008 member/minute
Mean Service Rate (μ)	0.2316 member/minute	0.2316 member/minute	0.2316 member/minute	0.2316 member/minute
Utilization factor of the entire system (ρ)	117.88%	78.58%	64.94%	64.94%
Probability of zero member in the system (P_0)	-	6.12%	21.26%	21.26%
Average number of members in the queue (L_q)	-	2.2908 members	0.9471 members	0.9471 members
Average number of members in the system (L_s)	-	4.6483 members	2.2459 members	2.2459 members
Average waiting time in the queue (W_q)	-	4.1956 minutes	3.1497 minutes	3.1497 minutes
Average time a member spends in the system (W_s)	-	8.5134 minutes	7.4665 minutes	7.4665 minutes

Table 7 interprets that for the membership section, it is advisable to have at least two (2) to four (4) frontliners available, depending on the time of day as indicated in the table above. Since three (3) frontliners suffice for efficient operation during most hours, the additional frontliner can assist other counters in different sections when extra help is required or in case of absences due to leaves or other activities. The table demonstrates

that operating with three (3) frontliners during the first batch enhances the utilization rate from 117.88% to 78.58%, resulting in 2.2908 members in the queue and 4.6483 members in the system. The average waiting time for members in the queue is 4.1956 minutes, while the average time spent by members in the system is 3.8433 minutes. During the second batch, both the current and proposed setups maintain two (2) counters open, as they can effectively operate without the need to add additional frontliners. With this allocation, the utilization rate is 64.94%. As a result, there are 0.9471 members in the queue and 2.2459 members in the system. The average waiting time for members in the queue is 3.1497 minutes, with members spending an average of 7.4665 minutes in the system.

Table 8.
Hourly Breaks' Performance Summary in Payment Section

Performance Rate	11:00 am – 12:00 pm		12:00 pm – 1:00 pm	
	Current	Proposed	Current	Proposed
Frontliner (s)	1	2	1	2
Mean Arrival Rate (λ)	0.1722 member/minute	0.1722 member/minute	0.1317 member/minute	0.1317 member/minute
Mean Service Rate (μ)	0.2373 member/minute	0.2373 member/minute	0.2373 member/minute	0.2373 member/minute
Utilization factor of the entire system (ρ)	72.57%	36.28%	55.50%	27.75%
Probability of zero member in the system (P_0)	27.43%	46.75%	44.50%	56.56%
Average number of members in the queue (L_q)	1.9195 members	0.1101 members	0.6922 members	0.0463 members
Average number of members in the system (L_s)	2.6452 members	0.8357 members	1.2472 members	0.6013 members
Average waiting time in the queue (W_q)	11.1469 minutes	0.6389 minutes	5.2556 minutes	0.3516 minutes
Average time a member spends in the system (W_s)	15.3610 minutes	4.854 minutes	9.4697 minutes	4.5657 minutes

Table 8 illustrates that for the payment section, it is essential to have at least two (2) frontliners available. This is based on the gathered data, which indicates that some members have numerous transactions lasting up to fourteen (14) minutes. This leads to longer waiting times for members in the queue. The table illustrates that operating with two (2) frontliners during the first batch increases the utilization rate from 72.57% to 36.28%, leading to 0.1101 members in the queue and 0.8357 members in the system. On average, members wait for 0.6389 minutes in the queue and spend 4.854 minutes in the system. During the second batch, maintaining two (2) counters open remains crucial, as this allocation raises the utilization rate from 55.50% to 27.75%. As a result, there are

0.0463 members in the queue and 0.6013 members in the system. On average, members wait for 0.3516 minutes in the queue and spend 4.5657 minutes in the system.

Proposed Frontliners' Schedule of Breaks

Table 9.

Proposed Third Batch Break's Performance Summary in Membership Section

Performance Rate	1:00 pm – 2:00 pm	
	Current	Proposed
Frontliner (s)	4	3
Mean Arrival Rate (λ)	0.4857 member/minute	0.4857 member/minute
Mean Service Rate (μ)	0.2316 member/minute	0.2316 member/minute
Utilization factor of the entire system (ρ)	52.43%	69.91%
Probability of zero member in the system (P_0)	11.73%	9.61%
Average number of members in the queue (L_q)	0.219 member	1.1404 members
Average number of members in the system (L_s)	2.3161 members	3.238 members
Average waiting time in the queue (W_q)	0.4508 minute	2.3479 minutes
Average time a member spends in the system (W_s)	4.7686 minutes	6.6657 minutes

Table 9 only focuses on the membership section due to a reduction in frontliners from four (4) to three (3) operating during the 1:00 pm – 2:00 pm shift, while the PACD/screening section and payment section continue to operate with two (2) frontliners during that time. The table illustrates that the proposed third batch and three (3) frontliners can still efficiently handle the service without forming long queues. The utilization factor increases from 52.43% to 69.91%, with 1.1494 members in the queue and 3.238 members in the system. The average waiting time per member is 2.3479 minutes, and 6.6657 minutes in the system.

Table 10.
Queuing System Comparison During Breaks: Discrete Event Simulation with AnyLogic Software Version 8.9

PACD/screeningsection											
Type	Frontliner	Time	Number of Arrivals	Member's Served	Member's time spent in the system (in mins)		Waiting Time (in mins)		Queue length		Utilization (%)
					Mean	Max	Mean	Max	Mean	Max	
Current	1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	85	43	13.32	30.75	12.369	30.74	15	42	99%
Proposed	2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm		71	3.62	7.44	2.329	6.077	3	9	79%
Current	1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	61	42	7.17	17.37	6.07	16.37	5	18	94%
Proposed	2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm		58	1.99	4.51	0.60	2.503	1	5	67%
Membership Section											
Type	Frontliner	Time	Number of Arrivals	Member's Served	Member's time spent in the system (in mins)		Waiting Time (min)		Queue length		Utilization (%)
					Mean	Max	Mean	Max	Mean	Max	
Current	2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	41	24	7.47	14.77	3.814	13.22	2	12	88%
Proposed	3	11:00 am - 12:00 pm		31	5.68	13.16	1.87	7.519	1	10	78%
Current	2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	14	13	5.86	12.18	1.36	6.068	0.4077	2	49%
Proposed	2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm		13							
Current	4	1:00 - 2:00 pm	36	28	4.44	7.89	0.19	2.361	0.0909	2	54%
Proposed	3	1:00 - 2:00 pm		27	4.88	8.60	1.15	6.18	1	6	69%
Payment Section											
Type	Frontliner	Time	Number of Arrivals	Member's Served	Member's time spent in the system (in mins)		Waiting Time (min)		Queue length		Utilization (%)
					Mean	Max	Mean	Max	Mean	Max	
Current	1	11:00 am - 12:00 pm	13	8	10.32	20.81	5.85	13.916	1	3	73%
Proposed	2	11:00 am - 12:00 pm		11	5.61	13.71	0.97	6.815	0.1670	1	39%
Current	1	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	7	5	9.89	20.81	4.14	13.916	1	2	52%
Proposed	2	12:00 pm - 1:00 pm		6	6.47	13.71	1.49	6.815	0.1960	1	29%

Discrete event simulation is utilized to optimize hourly break scheduling for frontliners by modeling event flows and analyzing different scenarios. Through simulating member arrivals, service times, and breaks, the impact of policies on queues and efficiency can be assessed. This method offers insights for achieving better resource balance and service quality. Table 10 presents real-life scenarios experienced by the agency, based on the number of available frontliners in each hour, comparing current and proposed schedules. The results indicate an increase in members served per hour, accompanied by reductions in member enrollment process duration, waiting time, and queue length. Moreover, there is a decrease in frontliner utilization, a critical factor in

preventing prolonged queues and waiting times. However, the results for the 1:00-2:00 pm period in the membership section differ from others due to a decrease in available counters by one to optimize scheduled breaks. This results in a slight increase in waiting time by one minute, which does not cause long queues or excessive waiting times and still adequately services members.

Table 11.
Proposed Frontliners' Schedule of Breaks

Sections Time/Frontliners	PACD/Screening		Membership				Payment	
	Frontliner 1	Frontliner 2	Frontliner 3	Frontliner 4	Frontliner 5	Frontliner 6	Frontliner 7	Frontliner 8
8:00 am - 9:00 am								
9:00 am - 10:00 am								
10:00 am - 11:00 am								
11:00 am - 12:00 pm								
12:00 pm - 1:00 pm								
1:00 pm - 2:00 pm								
2:00 pm - 3:00 pm								
3:00 pm - 4:00 pm								
4:00 pm - 5:00 pm								

Working
On Break
On Break, Operating by Backroom Employee 1
On Break, Operating by Backroom Employee 2
On Break, Operating by Backroom Employee 3
On Break, Operating by Backroom Employee 4

Table 10 illustrates the proposed scheduling of breaks for each frontliner operating in the agency. Since there are sixteen (16) backroom employees, with four (4) assigned to the membership section and twelve (12) to the Accounts Information Management Specialist, four (4) of them who are available and do not have a workload of tasks can be chosen to take over the shift while the frontliners are on breaks. Frontliner 1 will take his break at 1:00 pm, during which he will be substituted by backroom employee 1. Frontliner 2 will take a break at 12:00 pm, covered by backroom employee 2. Frontliner 3 will also take a break at 1:00 pm, while Frontliner 4 will do so at 11:00 am. Frontliners 5 and 6 will take their breaks at 12:00 pm. Frontliner 7 will have a break at 11:00 am, covered by backroom employee 3. Lastly, Frontliner 8 will take a break at 12:00 pm, and their responsibilities will be covered by backroom employee 4. This scheduling ensures that all frontliners have their breaks while maintaining a continuous flow of service with the appropriate number of counters available during these hours. Since the tasks of backliners are not overly burdensome, their breaks can still be accommodated during times when three frontliners can manage the workload.

Inadequate Requirements Dissemination in PACD/Screening Section

Figure .1

Comparison of Current and Proposed Flow Process Diagram: Membership Screening

Figure 1 illustrates a recommended method by proposing a checklist of requirements necessary for enrolling in membership. Before entering the PACD/screening section, members must complete the required forms and obtain necessary photocopies, such as their birth certificate and valid ID, to avoid forming long queues and cutting through lines. Observations indicate that some customers return multiple times to fulfill requirements, leading to wasted time and a decrease in morale. This repetition not only affects customer morale but also impacts frontline staff morale, as some members fail to complete the necessary forms.

Table 12.

Summary of Process Improvement Utilizing Checklist

Current	Proposed
Time Spent = 14.74 minutes	Time Spent = 11.64 minutes Reduced Time by 3.1 minutes (21.03%)
Distance Travelled = 334.3 feet	Distance Travelled = 272.14 feet Reduced Distance Travelled by 62.16 feet (18.59%)

From the Table 11, the summary of Process improvement proposed methods demonstrates a reduction in operational processes by one (1) and two (2) delays, thereby minimizing the time consumed in the process by 3.1 minutes marking a difference of 21.03% to the current process and the distance travelled by the member by 62.16 feet with a difference of 18.59% to the current process as well. During the observation period, it was noted that 31.99% of the members, equating to 119 out of 372, had missing requirements. The total saved time and distance amounted to 368.9 minutes, and 7397.04 feet travelled throughout the whole day. As a result, the processing time per member is faster, and the number of members repeating the process is reduced.

Numbering System in PACD/Screening Section

Figure 2.

Comparison of Current and Proposed Flow Process Diagram: Payment Screening

Figure 2 shows the recommended proposal is to establish separate queuing lines for the membership and payment sections. With two (2) frontliners operating throughout the day, each section can accommodate its own queue. Given that the number of members arriving for payment is lower compared to those applying for membership, the counter staff can also assist with payment transactions when there are no queues for payment.

Table 13.

Summary of Process Improvement Utilizing New Numbering System

Current	Proposed
Time Spent = 4.55 minutes	Time Spent = 3.09 minutes Reduced Time = 1.46 minutes (32.09%)

In Table 12 shows the summary of improvement, the recommended proposal of utilizing a new numbering queueing system demonstrates a reduction in time by 1.46 minutes, marking a difference of 32.09% to the current process, resulting in a total processing time of 3.09 minutes. This approach aims to prevent the formation of long queues, thereby providing a smoother flow of processing members.

Conclusions

The current queuing system at the case company, while generally effective, encounters challenges during specific periods, resulting in lengthy queues and increased wait times due to issues such as insufficient communication of requirements, inefficient frontliner break scheduling, and a lack of a streamlined numbering system. Analyzing frontliners' break scheduling and staff allocation underscores the importance of proper resource management for efficient service delivery. Proposing a balanced hourly staff allocation and a revised three-batch break schedule tailored to each department's needs aims to decrease wait times, optimize resource utilization, and enhance member satisfaction. Addressing the inadequate communication of requirements in the PACD/screening section is vital for improving the efficiency of the membership enrollment process. Implementing a checklist of necessary documents before entering the screening section reduces processing time and member travel distance, improving the overall enrollment process. Introducing a separate queuing system for the PACD/screening section aims to minimize wait times and enhance efficiency. By dedicating queue lines for each section and utilizing resources effectively, the proposed solution demonstrates significant improvements in processing time and overall service delivery.

Recommendations

The government health insurance agency is advised to implement a new queuing system in the Public Assistance and Complaints Desk (PACD)/Screening Section, developed by the Information Technology (IT) team, to improve member experience and alleviate confusion. This efficient system aims to streamline processes, reducing frustration and enhancing satisfaction. Furthermore, while considering the addition of another frontline counter in the payment section may seem beneficial for faster service,

Careful consideration is needed due to the potential increase in costs. Technological enhancements, such as installing kiosk machines for payments, can significantly reduce waiting times, improving efficiency. Incorporating posters and clear instructions outside the agency can help potential members prepare, saving time and effort. Additionally, directional signage within the agency can minimize confusion and ensure an organized flow of individuals, further enhancing the overall member experience. These recommendations aim to optimize operational processes and improve customer satisfaction at the government health insurance agency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were taken into account throughout the execution of this research. This encompasses the procedures of granting authorization and disclosing relevant data. The researcher addressed a letter to the corporation inquiring about their potential participation in the study, and the company gave their consent. To make the discussions accessible to the public, all names or personal identification were removed. To protect confidential information, the researchers have agreed to sign a non-disclosure agreement about the data obtained from the firm.

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